

Supplemental Tables & Figures for:

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Table S1. Sustainable practices that camp providers might engage in, grouped by five larger sustainability themes.

Theme	Specific Actions
<p>Sustainability Education & Communication (7 items)</p>	<p>Provide opportunities for campers to develop a lasting appreciation for the natural world Educate campers about the benefits of sustainable practices (energy and water conservation, waste reduction, etc.) Set expectations for campers to engage in sustainable behaviors Educate staff about the benefits of sustainable practices (energy and water conservation, waste reduction, etc.) Set expectations for staff to engage in and model sustainable behaviors Measure sustainable behavior change among campers and/or staff Grow food on site for educational purposes</p>
<p>Natural Resource & Wildlife Conservation (4 items)</p>	<p>Make your land more suitable for wildlife (pollinator gardens, bird houses, etc.) Minimize noise and/or light pollution to help wildlife Minimize environmental degradation during regular programming and/or new construction projects Monitor air and/or water quality</p>
<p>Purchasing & Procurement (3 items)</p>	<p>Intentionally buy “green” products (reusable or recyclable kitchenware, office supplies, cleaning supplies, etc.) Avoid purchasing single-use products that are not recyclable or compostable Purchase organic, local, or eco-friendly food</p>
<p>Waste Management (5 items)</p>	<p>Reduce kitchen waste produced by campers and/or staff Compost food waste Recycle waste produced by campers and/or staff Reuse camp resources (building materials, art supplies, old equipment, etc.) whenever possible Sustainably dispose of toxic materials (cleaning products, engine oil, batteries, etc.)</p>
<p>Energy & Water Consumption (7 items)</p>	<p>Use electricity from renewable energy sources (solar, wind, geothermal, etc.) Use energy efficient appliances (light bulbs, energy star appliances, etc.) Improve heating and cooling efficiency (regularly change air filters, regulate heating/cooling at off-peak times, etc.) Utilize fuel-efficient vehicles when making trips offsite (e.g., electric, hybrids) Use low-flow showers and/or toilets Capture and reuse rainwater and/or greywater Conduct periodic water/energy audits to track and monitor consumption</p>

Table S2. Potential barriers to environmental sustainability of camp providers, grouped by themes focused on resource constraints and other barriers.

Theme	Specific Actions
Lack of Resources (3 items)	Cost of implementation is too high Lack access to financial resources needed to become more sustainable Lack access to technological resources needed to become more sustainable
Other Barriers (7 items)	Enhancing sustainable practices is not a current priority Lack staff with the knowledge and skills needed to implement sustainable practices Camp infrastructure and/or setting does not support sustainable practices Decisions about sustainability priorities made at higher administrative levels Not aware of opportunities to enhance sustainability Don't know other organizations who might help us become more sustainable Other (specify)

Figure S1. Future sustainability ambitions reported by camp providers across the United States in 2021, including specific actions across five major sustainability themes: (a) Waste Management, (b) Sustainability Education and Communication, (c) Purchasing and Procurement, (d) Energy and Water Consumption, and (e) Natural Resource and Wildlife Conservation.

Table S3. Primary motivations for engaging in sustainable practices expressed by camp providers in the United States, based on qualitative data coding in response to the open-ended survey questions about motivations.

Sustainability Theme/Category	# of respondents	Quote
Environmental reasons (to protect natural resources and minimize environmental impacts)	16	“Our planet is on the verge of environmental collapse. Is there any other reason? Without a healthy planet, nothing else matters.”
Social reasons (to do the right thing and set a good example for campers and the community)	14	“I believe it is important to ‘practice what we preach’ and set a good example for campers. We can easily teach them everyday methods of resource conservation and sustainable practices that will have a wider impact on their home communities.”
Economic reasons (to save and/or make money)	5	“For the camp overall, economic motivators are probably first priority, because we need to stay open so that we can continue to provide a great place for kids to spend the summer.”
Religious	5	“To fulfill our biblical mandate to care for Creation and to model for campers and staff practical ways that care for the earth is foundational to our care for others.”

Table S4. Bivariate Pearson correlations depicting relationship between camp motivations to engage in sustainable practices and current participation in sustainable practices among camp organizations across the United States.

Sustainability Theme/Category	Environmental Motives	Social Motives	Economic Motives
Waste Management	0.225**	0.102	-0.006
Sustainability Education & Communication	0.279**	0.305***	-0.064
Natural Resource & Wildlife Conservation	0.186*	0.283**	0.016
Purchasing & Procurement	0.301***	0.225*	-0.113
Energy & Water Consumption	0.164	0.134	0.055

*, **, *** denote statistical significant of correlation coefficient at $p < 0.05$, 0.01 , and 0.001 , respectively

Table S5. Primary barriers to engaging in sustainable practices expressed by camp providers in the United States, based on qualitative data coding in response to the open-ended survey questions about barriers and constraints.

Sustainability Theme/Category	# of respondents	Quote
Lack of resources		
Lack access to financial resources needed	55	“I think the biggest barrier is perceived cost of implementing some of the bigger changes we need, like sustainable energy sources. Our leadership team & camp's owners are always open to making camp more ‘green’, but it is a business and sometimes it's hard to ‘do the right thing’”
Cost of implementation is too high		
Lack access to technological resources needed	0	
Other barriers		
Lack staff with the knowledge and skills needed to implement	21	“Having the time and manpower to sketch out all of these practices, and getting all staff members on board with new practices.”
Camp infrastructure and/or setting does not support it	12	“Access. For example our only commercial trash provider, does not support recycling in our area.”
Don’t know other organizations who might help us do it	0	
Enhancing sustainable practices is not a current priority	5	“Putting it at the top of a priority list that always seems like it's ranked on immediate need and not preventative planning.”
Decisions about sustainability priorities made at higher levels	13	“Decisions about sustainability priorities are made by the campground owner, not our camp (we are a rental).”
Not aware of opportunities to enhance sustainability	2	“Knowledge of all best practices and funds when applicable”
Other	5	“Availability of products, i.e., plastic is unavoidable”
COVID-19	7	“Covid-19 has greatly increased our consumption of single-use plastics due to sanitary concerns.”

Table S6. Bivariate Pearson correlations depicting relationship between constraints to engaging in sustainable practices and current participation in sustainable practices among camp organizations across the United States.

Sustainability Theme/Category	Lack of Resources	Other Barriers
Waste Management	-0.249**	-0.529***
Sustainability Education & Communication	-0.350***	-0.552***
Natural Resource & Wildlife Conservation	-0.269**	-0.409***
Purchasing & Procurement	-0.404***	-0.523***
Energy & Water Consumption	-0.209*	-0.400***

*, **, *** denote statistical significant of correlation coefficient at $p < 0.05$, 0.01 , and 0.001 , respectively